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TECHNICAL REQUIREMENTS FOR METADATA IN NFDI4ENERGY SERVICES
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Technical requirements for metadata in NFDI4Energy services

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General Information

Summary

Metadata is a key cornerstone of research data management. However, the proper use of metadata for both developers and users is not yet sufficiently developed. This deliverable shall present the current state of technical requirements that we encourage as NFDI4Energy. Its goal is to create guidance within the energy domain on how to interact with metadata and how to build systems and repositories that handle metadata. We also reflect on these kinds of requirements from other NFDI consortia, to show the similarities and differences that might arise from the different maturity and use cases throughout the different domains. The presented requirements reflect the state at the publication date, but will be further updated and evolved in the GitHub¹ repository that serves as a metadata requirement collection platform (<https://github.com/NFDI4Energy/metadata-requirements>). The repository is also meant for collecting requirements about metadata modules that are specific to certain dataset types. This requirement collection process will continue in the community over the next years. In order to contribute, use the GitHub issues in the repository to make your improvement ideas known.

Deliverable within NFDI4Energy

Task Area 4 of NFDI4Energy focuses on FAIR data for Energy System Research and all the aspects that are relevant to achieve it. The development of ontologies and metadata guidelines is among the core objectives. Measure 4.3 in this task area specifically focuses on the creation of metadata standards and guidelines that can be used to improve the annotation of energy research data with useful meta information. Furthermore, it shall define requirements on metadata handling throughout the services that NFDI4Energy is or will be providing. This deliverable provides an overview of the collected technical requirements for metadata in the energy domain that shall serve as guidelines for new services that are created to implement metadata creation and usage in a future-proof way. The requirements and guidelines are compared to the findings of other NFDI consortia to reflect on similarities and differences. Moreover, this deliverable shall act as a quick guidance on how to contribute to the metadata requirements that Measure 4.3 is collecting.

¹<https://github.com>

Requirement collection process

In the early stages of metadata requirements collection, we started by collecting ideas for technical requirements through a series of internal meetings. Through the discussions, we organized a workshop to collect metadata technical requirements at the Task Area 4 quarterly meeting. During the workshop, based on the development cycle of metadata standards, that is, design, implementation, integration, use, and review, participants of the workshop brainstormed and defined the technical requirements of the metadata. The technical requirements collected during the workshop were then classified and stored in a GitHub repository (<https://github.com/NFDI4Energy/metadata-requirements>). The details of the technical requirements are shown in the following sections. In addition to collecting technical requirements within NFDI4Energy, we also reviewed metadata guidelines from other NFDI consortia. This helped us to understand the similarities and differences that may arise from the different maturity and use cases across different domains.

Metadata guidelines of other parties

NFDI

The NFDI section “(Meta)data, Terminologies, Provenance”² has a task force “Metadata” that is looking into general advice towards Metadata usage in NFDI consortia. As different consortia and their respective research domains have quite different requirements, the work of the task force is focusing on the small part of core metadata that all domains have in common. This is focusing more on the general metadata fields instead of the technical requirements, as this is seen more as an implementation detail and is mostly handled by the individual data platforms and repositories. However, in the future, there might be common guidelines on the technical level as well. Several domains like biology, medicine and physics already have various extensive data repositories in place that do not necessarily use interoperable metadata standards. This means, the focus in established domains is more on interoperability than on the mere technical requirements, since that can cause issues when trying to change existing ways of large sub-communities. In contrast, domains that are still trying to bring forth commonly accepted data repositories are more often in search of a good solution for handling metadata in general, and are therefore much more open to discussions about the technical requirements of metadata that are presented in this deliverable.

Base4NFDI

The NFDI Base services are not a domain-specific consortium, but instead provide services that are useful to all NFDI consortia. As one of their goals, Base4NFDI is interested in providing technical solutions that can make metadata more usable in the future. For example, the Terminology Service for NFDI (TS4NFDI)[1] helps to solve an essential problem of metadata by providing controlled vocabularies including a web-based widget for certain input fields. As a conclusion, the use of controlled vocabularies and the means to extend on existing vocabularies is also a metadata requirement to Base4NFDI.

NFDI4Ing

NFDI4Ing has a working group “Metadata4Ing” that also created an ontology with the same name to be able to specify how metadata shall work for the engineering domain [2]. This includes a modularized approach that also fits the requirements collected for NFDI4Energy. The metadata ontology of NFDI4Ing can be found online. Additionally, the AIMS software (an extension of COSCINE³) from RWTH was developed in relation to NFDI4Ing to manage resource-type-based (modularized) metadata schemas.

²<https://www.nfdi.de/section-meta/?lang=en>

³<https://coscine.rwth-aachen.de/>

GHGA

The German Human Genome-Phenome Archive (GHGA), an NFDI consortium, published a domain-specific metadata schema in September 2023 [3]. This schema was adapted from the commonly-used European Genome-Phenome Archive (EGA) Metadata Schema. Entities are organized in seven modules, each designed to document different types of information, with entity properties categorized as Required, Recommended, or Optional. Existing ontologies and controlled vocabularies are used to define the allowable entries for certain metadata properties. These features of the GHGA Metadata Schema are noteworthy as they align with the requirements of the NFDI4Energy Metadata Schema.

NFDI4Biodiversity

NFDI4Biodiversity does not develop its own standards or specify technical requirements, as the domain already uses several existing metadata standards (Access to Biological Collection Data (ABCD), PANGAEA PanSimple⁴, DarwinCore Archive (DwC-A), Common Data Model-light (CDM-light)⁵ and BioSchemas⁶). Instead, the focus lies on creating interoperability between the standards by creating a conversion service [4].

NFDI4BIOIMAGE

The NFDI4BIOIMAGE consortium has worked on generating mappings between existing metadata standards for existing research data management tools to improve interoperability. This is critical for datasets which include both bioimaging data and measurement data, and are therefore unsuitable for storage in repositories designed for only one or the other data type. Efforts have focused on mapping the Recommended Metadata for Biological Images (REMBI) schema for use with the community-standard OMERO⁷ research data management platform [5], and on mapping the metadata schema of the Annotated Research Context (ARC)⁸ format to OMERO [6]. Additionally, the consortium pursues the further development of a bioimaging standard that uses RDF-based metadata [7], which also fits the NFDI4Energy perspective.

NFDI4Chem

NFDI4Chem proposes several technical metadata guidelines that fit the NFDI4Energy ideas. The use of controlled vocabularies, a split into modularized metadata, published FAIR metadata schemas, metadata record validation, and the mapping between existing standards are similarities that are mentioned several times[8][9][10][11][12]. Additionally, some more similarities include the use of agreed upon terminology[9], persistent identifiers [8] and good documentation [13]. There are also some points that propose additional requirements, like the use of a schema service to allow users to build and inherit from schemas and use them in a modified way[10]. Furthermore, the use of a Request for Comments (RFC) is proposed as a means to find consensus for metadata [8].

PUNCH4NFDI

PUNCH4NFDI has published a report on metadata schemas and what requirements apply for the PUNCH community [14]. It contains several requirements that are different from the ones presented for NFDI4Energy, which are grounded in the different environment of that research domain, especially the existence of big experiment-based databases of physics research data that have already existed for several decades and use dedicated data formats. The only similarity can be found in the possibility to link between data sets, such that it is possible to find related or similar data sets. Different requirements include a layer-based structure for metadata from level 0 to 7 and an explicit focus on long-term storage of the large amounts of research data and their metadata as well. Fur-

⁴<https://ws.pangaea.de/schemas/pansimple/pansimple.xsd>

⁵<https://data.bgbm.org/dataset/gfbio/0027/Manual-EDIT-Platform-Appendix-CDM-Light-2.04.pdf>

⁶<https://bioschemas.org/>

⁷<https://www.openmicroscopy.org/omero/>

⁸<https://github.com/nfdi4plants/ARC-specification>

thermore, PUNCH4NFDI states an explicit need for describing all data processing steps in metadata and recommending the correct software and version to use an annotated data set.

NFDI4Earth

NFDI4Earth did also publish a list of recommendations on metadata similar to this deliverable, but with a less technical focus [15]. Similarities include the use of unique identifiers for each metadata record, modular domain-specific metadata extensions based on the resource type, and the ability to link between metadata records. Additionally, metadata must be accessible via standard protocols and well-known formats, such as the Open Archives Initiative Protocol for Metadata Harvesting (OAI-PMH). Also, the importance of user feedback is stated to be an essential part of metadata handling.

Differences to this deliverable can be seen in the need to provide a value policy, especially for non-controlled vocabularies, to ensure consistency and standardization. Implementing separate licenses for data and metadata is important to establish clear legal boundaries, and usage rights also extend the scope of the current NFDI4Energy requirements. Another topic is that visualization of provenance information is essential to understand the origin and history of data [16]. Furthermore, the organization of metadata in a hierarchy is proposed.

Specific scenarios of NFDI4Earth include the ability to scrape metadata from datasets, which can significantly reduce manual effort and improve accuracy. There is a focus on relational databases to add metadata for foreign keys, ensuring better data integration and management [17]. Lastly, NFDI4Earth provides a certification for data registries in their domain, ensuring that data repositories meet certain standards and are reliable [18].

GAIA-X

GAIA-X⁹ is used as an umbrella term for several research projects, e.g. one that focuses on future mobility data spaces. It is not affiliated with NFDI directly, but faces similar challenges. NFDI4Energy has been in contact with the future mobility GAIA-X project, which is intended to provide requirements and potential implementation solutions for data spaces in the mobility sector, so that they can be established for municipalities in Germany and Europe. In general, they have identified several design principles that services and data spaces should follow to contribute to interoperability between different vendors. There are several similarities with the technical metadata requirements presented in this deliverable. The design principles are described in a conference publication from 2024 [19]. They also propose the use of modularized metadata depending on the respective use case, which is built with semantic models to form a metadata knowledge graph. Moreover, they propose the use of Smart Data Models¹⁰ as a foundation to build semantic metadata modules. To improve simplicity and ease of access of existing processes, they heavily focus on the use of artificial intelligence for semantic entity and relation extraction from natural language, which they see as a game-changer to adapt legacy systems easily, as it can work on text documents and still produce meaningful semantic metadata.

BERD@NFDI

BERD@NFDI does not explicitly propose technical guidelines for metadata, but they do have their own metadata schema to be used with their data portal. The schema is based on DataCite and therefore also follows the guideline to use existing terms as much as possible. Furthermore, another way to think about metadata requirements is to look at FAIR assessment tools and what criteria they check, to be a requirement for metadata [20][21]. Another new idea includes the use of large language models for metadata creation where possible to simplify the metadata creation process [22].

⁹<https://gaia-x.eu/>

¹⁰<https://smartdatamodels.org/>

KonsortSWD

KonsortSWD uses their own data format to combine data and metadata, in order to fulfill their technical requirement that data and metadata are stored together. The metadata is stored as XML which conforms to Data Documentation Initiative (DDI) metadata specifications[23]. They also provide an extension for this format to also showcase some kind of modularity as well as the use of controlled vocabularies [24]. Furthermore, they also recommend the use of OAI-PMH to exchange metadata [25]. The policy on non-controlled metadata fields e.g. title and description are also mentioned as a guideline [26].

NFDI4Culture

NFDI4Culture proposes a knowledge-graph-based metadata infrastructure that uses the Basic Formal Ontology (BFO) and NFDIcore ontologies as a foundation [27].

NFDI4Memory

The NFDI4Memory consortium focuses on improving metadata quality and interoperability for historical research data. They aim to improve the adoption of established standards such as Text Encoding Initiative (TEI), Lightweight Information Describing Objects (LIDO), and International Committee on Documentation - Conceptual Reference Model (CIDOC-CRM) [28].

NFDI4Objects

NFDI4Objects proposes the use of a metadata discovery service to improve the general accessibility of the metadata itself, as well as the referenced data sets [29]. Furthermore, they started to create an ontology for terminologies that is required in the metadata context, and they also want to identify a minimal metadata set that ensures interoperability across different systems by aligning with existing standards like CIDOC-CRM, schema.org, and Simple Knowledge Organisation System (SKOS), while allowing for flexible adaptations to diverse research needs [30], [31].

Text+

The Text+ consortium recommends the usage of established standards like Dublin Core, DataCite, MARC 21¹¹, Open Language Archives Community (OLAC)¹² or TEI. The choice should be made depending on the application context. Additionally, they also recommend the use of the Component MetaData Infrastructure (CMDI) to manage any use-case-specific metadata extensions [32].

NFDI4Health

In the health sector, there are many different kinds of studies performed and the relevant information about observations can be quite diverse. NFDI4Health has created a common metadata schema (MDS) to create a common way of annotating diverse data records [33]. It is based on several established standards such as ClinicalTrials.gov, the German Clinical Trials Register, the International Clinical Trials Registry, Fast Healthcare Interoperability Resources (FHIR) from Health Level 7 (HL7), Minimum Information About Biobank data Sharing (MIABIS), the Maelstrom Research cataloging toolkit, and DDI Controlled Vocabularies. This schema and all its submodules are hosted on the schema management service provided by the Center for Expanded Data Annotation and Retrieval (CEDAR). Furthermore, there is a plan to produce Resource Description Framework (RDF) exports to create an interface to other NFDI consortia.

DAPHNE4NFDI

DAPHNE4NFDI proposes the use of SciCat¹³, an open source metadata catalog solution, to tackle the challenges of data curation as the volume of collected data is increasing. It can manage diverse

¹¹<https://www.loc.gov/marc/bibliographic/>

¹²<http://www.language-archives.org/OLAC/metadata.html>

¹³<https://www.scicatproject.org/>

data types and be customized based on user needs. It does support direct API access as well as an OAI-PMH export interface [34]. There are also some recommendations for a metadata schema which does focus more on content and not on technical requirements [35].

FAIRmat

FAIRmat is using NOMAD¹⁴. The used metadata schema in NOMAD is described in [36]. This also states that the metadata schema should be conceptual and that the records can have different representations depending on the respective use case.

NFDI4CAT

NFDI4CAT favors the use of RDF to model metadata, the Shapes Constraint Language (SHACL) as a validation language and the modeling of LinkML¹⁵ shapes as templates for metadata records. This shall be based on DCAT-AP and shall also provide entity relationship diagrams for documentation purposes [37]. Furthermore, a common vocabulary that can serve for controlled vocabularies is being developed [38]. Lastly, there is an official whitepaper about ontology-based data management and interoperability [39] that covers many metadata-related topics, like persistent identifiers, validation of metadata and the storage and querying via triple stores.

MaRDI

Mathematics is a field of research that has only little similarities with many of the domains discussed above and have special requirements on metadata for their data sets. There is little to no information available in this regard.

DataPLANT

DataPLANT offers a suite of Research Data Management (RDM) services for plant research. It provides a collaborative platform, PLANTdataHUB, for managing research data, and tools for managing ARCs [40]. DataPLANT also provides a metadata recommendation quiz to help researchers find the metadata checklists and endpoint repositories best suited to their data.

FAIRagro

FAIRagro focuses on agricultural systems research, especially in areas related to the development of sustainable crop production in current and future agroecosystems. Within FAIRagro, there are two measures that work on different areas of metadata standards. The first focuses on standards for digital resources, and the other focuses on standards for data management, FAIRness, and discoverability. FAIRagro has published a document[41] on metadata standards. In the published document, FAIRagro provides a detailed list of metadata standards and has extended Schema.org to further enhance the interoperability of data in the agrosystem domain by including BioSchemas.

NFDI4Immuno

NFDI4Immuno aims to build an open infrastructure for FAIR RDM. As introduced in [42], NFDI4Immuno defines data classes and data types to clearly distinguish between the biological property and the device that was used to measure the property. It also introduces a two-layered metadata model, in which the first layer is biological metadata and the second layer is data-type metadata.

NFDIxCS

NFDIxCS has developed the Research Data Management Container [43], which encapsulates research data, software, and execution environments in a single container to provide a portable unit for management, distribution, and access control.

¹⁴<https://nomad-lab.eu/nomad-lab/>

¹⁵<https://linkml.io/>

NFDI-MatWerk

NFDI-MatWerk has provided several tools and services for metadata management [44]. For example, Base Repo and Metastore are used to store and manage data and its metadata, ensuring that data is stored long-term and easily accessible. The Typed PID Maker and the FAIR Digital Object Lab provide support for creation and management of data objects. Additionally, the metadata Standards Catalog and Data Collections Explorer help researchers choose suitable metadata standards and find relevant data collections.

NFDI4DataScience

NFDI4DataScience focuses on the areas of machine learning and data science. It has published several reports related to metadata alignment. In [45], NFDI4DataScience combined the generic DataCite with the domain-specific metadata standard, such as BioSchemas, to improve the ability to search and share research data across different fields. In another report [46], NFDI4DataScience published the results of aligning the machine-actionable Software Management Plans (maSMP) metadata schema with the Research Software MetaData Guidelines (RSMD). This alignment helps improve the metadata quality of research software. NFDI4DataScience also released a metadata dataset [47] of Hugging face model cards and created crosswalk tables [48] for machine learning models and datasets used for training. Additionally, NFDI4DataScience proposed a flexible approach to metadata quality assessment [49]. It uses Piveau, a data management ecosystem, to assess the quality of metadata in the research portal, and ensure its compliance with the FAIR principles.

Requirements for Metadata in NFDI4Energy

NFDI4Energy is collecting requirements on GitHub. There are several repositories for this purpose and the metadata requirements can be found under the following URL: <https://github.com/NFDI4Energy/metadata-requirements>.

This includes both functional and technical requirements. The focus of this document lies exclusively on the technical requirements.

All the collected requirements are classified according to two dimensions. First is the general topic, whether the requirement is more about a metadata schema, a metadata record or additional tooling. The second dimension specifies the lifecycle step of the respective item: Design, Implementation, Integration, Use or Review. Figure 1 shows this classification, as well as the number of requirements that match the given combination. There is one cell in this matrix that stand out particularly: The design phase of a metadata record does not really exist. The design rather happens for the schema instead of the record.

The following section will cover the meanings of the individual cells in the matrix.

Classification explanations

The metadata schema describes everything that is done to the model of metadata, while the metadata record is considered an instance of that model. The tooling always contains requirements about tools that can or shall be used during a given lifecycle step, either for the metadata schema or metadata records.

The **design phase** considers the thoughts that are necessary to define relevant fields of metadata, specify if they need controlled values, etc. That is also why the metadata record does not really have a design phase because it solely depends on the design of the schema.

The **implementation phase** considers the technical creation and publication of a schema and its records. This includes for example the selected serialization formats and public URL.

The **integration phase** focuses on all the necessary tasks around the preparation for use of a schema and its records within an application. Therefore, this is mostly relevant for software developers.

	Design	Implementation	Integration	Use	Review
Schema	6	1	2	5	2
Records	↑	3	1	4	1
Tooling	2	1	2	1	3

Figure 1: Technical Metadata Requirement Dimension Matrix

The **use phase** contains requirements that need to be followed when users shall be working with the schema or its records directly - either by creating them or accessing them. This also includes learning about the meanings of fields etc. in the form of documentation.

Even though it is listed last, the **review phase** is not necessarily the last one from a temporal standpoint, as reviews and improvements to existing metadata schemas and records can happen at any time. In general, the requirements of this phase target the improvement and update process of the respective component over time.

At the time of writing, an endeavor to improve the requirement specification of NFDI4Energy is underway. The publicly available requirements will be updated accordingly in the future.

List of technical requirements of Metadata in NFDI4Energy

Metadata Schema

Links between metadata records

Lifecycle	Design
Topic	Metadata Schema
ID	REQ-DESIGN-SCHEMA-LINKED-METADATA
Description	Help users to traverse semantically linked metadata records that are similar, different, related, etc. This can involve data from the same or different project, a similar purpose or an explicitly specified difference. This can be achieved using an explicit field for links in the metadata schema
Creation date	2024-08-15
Linked terms	http://purl.org/dc/elements/1.1/relation http://purl.org/dc/terms/isReferencedBy http://purl.org/dc/terms/isRequiredBy http://purl.org/dc/terms/references http://purl.org/dc/terms/requires https://datacite-metadata-schema.readthedocs.io/en/4.6/properties/relatedidentifier/ https://datacite-metadata-schema.readthedocs.io/en/4.6/properties/relateditem/ DCAT also uses DC terms
Solution idea	Provide a generic metadata module in the schema that focuses on relations to other datasets and think about a good collection of relations between them.
Priority	Low

The metadata schema reuses agreed upon terms and semantics

Lifecycle	Design
Topic	Metadata Schema
ID	REQ-DESIGN-SCHEMA-REUSE-AGREED-SEMANTICS
Description	It is vital to not create duplicate definitions to improve interoperability. This should be done using pre-existing ontologies wherever possible
Creation date	2024-09-17
Linked terms	https://schema.org/sameAs http://www.w3.org/2004/02/skos/core#related http://www.w3.org/2004/02/skos/core#exactMatch (and other match types)
Solution idea	Importing / Referencing of all ontologies that provide useful terms or semantics
Priority	High

Fields in the schema shall use controlled vocabularies as much as possible

Lifecycle	Design
Topic	Metadata Schema
ID	REQ-DESIGN-SCHEMA-CONTROLLED-VOCABULARIES
Description	Prevent the interoperability issues that arise with custom human input, by using controlled vocabularies for user input where possible
Creation date	2024-08-15
Linked terms	https://json-schema.org/draft/2020-12/json-schema-validation#name-pattern http://www.w3.org/ns/shacl#class http://www.w3.org/ns/shacl#nodeKind http://www.w3.org/ns/shacl#sparql
Solution idea	Use either ENUM like instances of a type in OWL or specify a base class for terms as child classes, use public identifiers of a certain pattern (e.g. purl, DOI, orcid, etc.) - multiple solutions will be necessary. Consider using Terminology services or special term lookup services like the DBpedia Lookup
Priority	High

Fields need to be categorized by importance

Lifecycle	Design
Topic	Metadata Schema
ID	REQ-DESIGN-SCHEMA-FIELD-IMPORTANCE
Description	To allow users to quickly grasp which metadata fields are more important we need to cluster them into mandatory, optional, etc.
Creation date	2024-10-22
Linked terms	https://datacite-metadata-schema.readthedocs.io/en/4.6/properties/overview/#levels-of-obligation https://www.dcat-ap.de/def/dcatde/3.0/spec/#verbindlichkeitsstufen
Solution idea	Additional attribute for all metadata fields (compare OEM Badges)
Priority	Medium

Modularity

Lifecycle	Design
Topic	Metadata Schema
ID	REQ-DESIGN-SCHEMA-MODULARITY
Description	To ensure a good quality of metadata for a given entity it is important to have specifically tailored sets of metadata fields. It makes sense to group several fields together if they always appear in a common context. Each of these modules needs to have a precise and limited scope. Smaller is often better in this context.
Creation date	2024-10-22
Linked terms	http://www.w3.org/2004/02/skos/core#ConceptScheme http://www.w3.org/2004/02/skos/core#inScheme
Solution idea	Cluster metadata fields in modules and allow one entity to be annotated by a set of these modules. A strategy to find the correct modules needs to be worked out
Priority	High

Language

Lifecycle	Design
Topic	Metadata Schema
ID	REQ-DESIGN-SCHEMA-LANGUAGE
Description	Since key value maps only see a key equal if it matches 100% it is necessary to have all keys in a common language. We propose to use only English names for the keys. If a serialization format allows multiple languages also other languages can be supported, but English must have the highest priority
Creation date	2024-10-22
Linked terms	http://purl.org/dc/elements/1.1/language https://datacite-metadata-schema.readthedocs.io/en/4.6/properties/language/ Note that these links are focusing on a language of a resource while this requirement focuses more on the design of the metadata schema
Solution idea	Just use English keys for the fields and perform translations only with annotation properties
Priority	High

Provided schema files

Lifecycle	Implementation
Topic	Metadata Schema
ID	REQ-IMPL-SCHEMA-PROVIDED-FILES
Description	A formalized specification of the schema is necessary. The preferred format is in a semantic format like Turtle/Notation3. Additionally, the schema files shall be provided as JSON schema (both plain JSON and JSON-LD) as a convenience for external use cases. Only the semantic format can be considered the root schema and the others must be updated on every change respectively. These types of formats are prioritized because of their validation and form generation capabilities
Creation date	2024-09-23
Linked terms	N/A
Solution idea	JSON-Schema files can be generated from an OWL/SHACL specification of the root schema
Priority	High

Allow interoperability between existing metadata standards

Lifecycle	Integration
Topic	Metadata Schema
ID	REQ-INTEGRATION-SCHEMA-STANDARD-INTEROPERABILITY
Description	Metadata records for our schema should be easily interoperable with other platforms that use different schemas, as it prevents re-annotation of metadata in other formats and supports data access to and from other platforms
Creation date	2024-08-15
Linked terms	https://www.getty.edu/publications/categories-description-works-art/metadata-standards-crosswalk/ https://www.ukoln.ac.uk/metadata/interoperability/ http://www.w3.org/2004/02/skos/core# http://ns.inria.org/edoal/1.0/ https://faircore4eosc.eu/eosc-core-components/metadata-schema-and-crosswalk-registry-mscr
Solution idea	Schema crosswalks to the most relevant standards are helpful for federated searches and form a foundation of format conversions. Scripts shall be provided to convert from and to our schema for a selected set of standards. Evaluate formalized (semantic) formats for crosswalks and recommend one that can be integrated into existing knowledge graphs / ontologies.
Priority	Medium

Guidelines for applications using the metadata schema

Lifecycle	Integration
Topic	Metadata Schema
ID	REQ-INTEGRATION-SCHEMA-APPLICATION-GUIDELINES
Description	Allow developers to get going with the schema quickly with a clear set of requirements or guidelines on how to integrate and work with the metadata schema. All applications that want to work with the standard are obliged to follow these guidelines.
Creation date	2024-08-15
Linked terms	N/A
Solution idea	Extrapolate a subset of the requirements on this page and format them on some kind of online documentation.
Priority	Low

Online documentation

Lifecycle	Use
Topic	Metadata Schema
ID	REQ-USE-SCHEMA-DOCUMENTATION
Description	Each metadata module / profile, and each individual metadata field shall have a definition and description text that is available online.
Creation date	2024-08-15
Linked terms	https://w3id.org/arco/ontology/context-description/Documentation http://dev.poderopedia.com/vocab/Documentation https://w3id.org/loin#Documentation https://w3id.org/semsys/ns/swemls#hasDocumentation https://w3id.org/vair#TechnicalDocumentation http://meta.icos-cp.eu/ontologies/cpmeta/hasDocumentationUri
Solution idea	Generated documentation on GitHub pages
Priority	high

Usage guide

Lifecycle	Use
Topic	Metadata Schema
ID	REQ-USE-SCHEMA-USAGE-GUIDE
Description	The metadata schema needs to be accompanied by an online documentation or guide on how to use it properly. This shall include different user perspectives including but not limited to data owners, application developers and data registry maintainers. Also, it needs to motivate why the usage of metadata and respective standards is important.
Creation date	2024-08-15
Linked terms	http://www.w3.org/ns/lemon/ontolex#usage http://rdvocab.info/RDARelationshipsWEMI/guide http://def.seegrid.csiro.au/isotc211/iso19115/2003/metadata#Usage http://purl.org/olia/ubyCat.owl#usage
Solution idea	Additional Markdown based documentation that can accompany the generated GitHub pages.
Priority	medium

Visualize different use of terminology among reused / mapped schemas and ontologies

Lifecycle	Use
Topic	Metadata Schema
ID	REQ-USE-SCHEMA-DOCUMENTATION-TERMINOLOGY-DIFFERENCES
Description	Some terms are used differently between different standards or use different names for the same thing. The documentation shall provide a way to recognize those cases, to help users understand the differences of similar terms
Creation date	2024-08-15
Linked terms	http://open.vocab.org/terms/similarTo http://vocab.deri.ie/cogs#TerminologicalMapping http://www.w3.org/ns/lemon/vartrans#TerminologicalRelation
Solution idea	Use terminology from thesauri or SKOS to express "similarTerms", "similarBut-Different" and "notToBeConfusedWith" relations.
Priority	medium

Schema documentation shall be understandable for users that need to fill or read metadata

Lifecycle	Use
Topic	Metadata Schema
ID	REQ-USE-SCHEMA-DOCUMENTATION-STAKEHOLDER-USERS
Description	The schema documentation must provide helpful information to users without semantics or metadata background, so it should not just be focused around developers
Creation date	2024-08-15
Linked terms	http://dev.poderopedia.com/vocab/hasOtherDocumentation https://w3id.org/arco/ontology/context-description/DocumentationType
Solution idea	This is hard to measure, so for now just involve end users in the design of the documentation.
Priority	Medium

Allow for a curated way to extend controlled vocabularies

Lifecycle	Use
Topic	Metadata Schema
ID	REQ-USE-SCHEMA-CURATED-CONTROLLED-VOCABS
Description	Strict controlled vocabularies can cause frustration for users, if they are unable to correctly express the meta information that would be best suited. Free text can sometimes describe better what a certain artifact / dataset is about, if there are no matching values in the controlled vocabulary. However, free text causes interoperability issues, so it is necessary to provide a process that allows to add new items to a controlled vocabulary in a curated way, that does not hinder the workflow of the user
Creation date	2024-08-15
Linked terms	https://www.w3.org/TR/shacl/#InConstraintComponent
Solution idea	Embedding a terminology search into a metadata input form when there can be no proper choice made to find a reference in an ontology for a term. If the term from the other ontology fulfills yet to be determined characteristics it might be possible to extend the vocabulary with that term (initially for the time the form is active) and on a long run the added "external" terms could be curated and either accepted or revoked centrally for the schema.
Priority	Medium

Documentation shall clearly show the terms used from other ontologies / schemas

Lifecycle	Review
Topic	Metadata Schema
ID	REQ-REVIEW-SCHEMA-DOCUMENTATION-CLEAR-REFERENCES
Description	Documentation should reference terms from other ontologies and schemas to maximize interoperability, providing clear links to the original sources and formal specifications. This approach ensures consistent terminology and enables seamless integration with external systems, enhancing the metadata's usability across diverse platforms. It also increases the awareness of users about the origins of each metadata field.
Creation date	2024-08-15
Linked terms	https://schema.org/about https://schema.org/itemReviewed https://schema.org/reviewAspect https://schema.org/author https://schema.org/reviewBody https://schema.org/mentions https://schema.org/citation
Solution idea	Use Markdown and HTML to incorporate named links to external sources. Schema terms can be embedded as metadata tags or structured annotations where applicable.
Priority	High

Metadata schema / standard needs to have a clear versioning scheme

Lifecycle	Review
Topic	Metadata Schema
ID	REQ-REVIEW-SCHEMA-VERSIONING
Description	Implement a clear versioning scheme to ensure that each dataset is accurately linked to the correct schema version. This enables consistency, traceability, and compatibility across systems. The versioning system should include identifiers for major, minor, and patch updates. Each version should also link to release notes and modification dates where applicable. The current and all older versions must be accessible via a GUPRI.
Creation date	2024-08-15
Linked terms	https://schema.org/version https://schema.org/releaseNotes https://schema.org/dateModified
Solution idea	Use semantic versioning (e.g., MAJOR.MINOR.PATCH) and reference the used version in the metadata schema, so each record can be clearly referenced to the used version.
Priority	High

Tooling

Metadata Schema Implementation Tools

Lifecycle	Design
Topic	Tooling
ID	REQ-DESIGN-TOOLING-STATE-OF-THE-ART
Description	The Metadata schema shall be created and maintained using state-of-the-art tools of the semantic web domain
Creation date	2024-09-23
Linked terms	https://protege.stanford.edu/ https://github.com
Solution idea	The core metadata schema shall be edited in Protégé. The metadata schema shall be stored on GitHub in a dedicated repository in the NFDI4Energy organization.
Priority	High

Metadata Schema Improvement Tools

Lifecycle	Design
Topic	Tooling
ID	REQ-DESIGN-TOOLING-IMPROVEMENT
Description	To enhance the interoperability of the metadata schema with other metadata schemas and improve the overall quality of metadata, it is important to try to reuse existing terms. Finding these can be aided with the use of terminology search and cross-walks between metadata standards. The used design tools shall assist the developer in applying these mechanisms.
Creation date	2024-09-23
Linked terms	It seems existing plugins are too old to work
Solution idea	Protégé can be used to edit the metadata schema. Protégé could have useful plugins for terminology search from important other metadata standards. Otherwise, a plugin might be configurable against a DBpedia Lookup or the NFDI terminology service that was initialized with common metadata standards.
Priority	Medium

Metadata record creation service

Lifecycle	Implementation
Topic	Tooling
ID	REQ-IMPL-TOOLING-RECORD-CREATION-SERVICE
Description	To ensure that the creation of metadata records can be done easily from different application contexts a service solution for the creation can be beneficial. So this service could be embedded via an application plugin. Such a service can therefore support multiple programming languages.
Creation date	2024-09-23
Linked terms	N/A
Solution idea	Metadata record creation and editing as a web service.
Priority	Medium

Metadata Integration Tools

Lifecycle	Integration
Topic	Tooling
ID	REQ-INTEGRATION-TOOLING-METADATA-FLEXIBILITY-FOR-APPLICATIONS
Description	A unified metadata schema used by the tools shall provide capabilities that allow each tool to customize the schema within certain limits to be best suited for the given use case of the tool. For example tools should be able to define explicit rules for what metadata fields are necessary and which are optional. Also, the use of certain domain-specific metadata schemas/modules should be controllable, ensuring that relevant metadata is captured.
Creation date	2024-09-23
Linked terms	https://w3id.org/squap/SoftwareQuality/FlexibilityInUse https://w3id.org/dco#FlexibilityService
Solution idea	The input forms for metadata should be somehow generated. This might require inputs from the developer on what metadata modules are relevant and if certain fields should have a non-standard mandatory state. This could work best with a service that produces metadata forms that can be configured via the parameters to the endpoint
Priority	Medium

Provide export capabilities

Lifecycle	Integration
Topic	Tooling
ID	REQ-INTEGRATION-TOOLING-STANDARD-EXPORTS
Description	To boost compatibility and interoperability it is necessary to provide exports in a selection of well established metadata standards
Creation date	2024-10-22
Linked terms	https://w3id.org/squap/SoftwareQuality/Compatibility https://w3id.org/squap/SoftwareQuality/Interoperability
Solution idea	Use formalized crosswalks to perform a conversion to classic standards like DCT, DataCite, ...
Priority	Medium

Metadata Integration Tools

Lifecycle	Use
Topic	Tooling
ID	REQ-USE-TOOLING-CONVERSION-SERVICE
Description	Provide a tool that supports metadata record conversion from one schema to another, enabling easy integration for tool developers, even if their existing tools are built around a different metadata schema. This tool should facilitate interoperability across multiple schemas, reducing the burden on developers to manually map terms or fields.
Creation date	2024-09-23
Linked terms	https://schema.org/Thing https://schema.org/convertTo https://schema.org/targetFormat http://purl.org/dc/terms/conformsTo http://purl.org/dc/terms/format http://purl.org/dc/terms/relation https://www.w3.org/TR/prov-o/#wasDerivedFrom https://www.w3.org/TR/prov-o/#hadPrimarySource https://www.w3.org/ns/dcat#mediaType https://www.w3.org/TR/vocab-dcat-2/#Class http://edamontology.org/format_1915 http://edamontology.org/operation_0335 http://www.w3.org/2004/02/skos/core#exactMatch http://www.w3.org/2004/02/skos/core#closeMatch
Solution idea	Consider using existing ontology matching tools to perform schema mapping, which can be used as foundation to automate much of the metadata record conversion process.
Priority	Medium

Version control shall be applied for documentation

Lifecycle	Review
Topic	Tooling
ID	REQ-REVIEW-TOOLING-DOCUMENTATION-VERSION-CONTROL
Description	Apply version control to the metadata schema documentation. This will improve documentation quality, make changes to documentation traceable, and prevent losses when edits are made by multiple people.
Creation date	2024-09-19
Linked terms	https://schema.org/version https://schema.org/UpdateAction
Solution idea	GitHub is a good foundation for the documentation source files and can also host the actual online documentation
Priority	medium

Metadata Versioning Tools

Lifecycle	Review
Topic	Tooling
ID	REQ-REVIEW-TOOLING-VERSIONING
Description	Apply version control to the metadata schema. This will improve schema quality, make changes to the schema traceable, and prevent losses when edits are made by multiple people. New versions shall come with migration scripts to convert existing entries to the new version of the schema.
Creation date	2024-09-23
Linked terms	https://schema.org/version https://schema.org/schemaVersion https://schema.org/UpdateAction
Solution idea	The metadata schema can be versioned using git tags, in this way, the persistent URLs of the metadata schema files will contain the respective version number. Each new release of the schema must be checked with analysis tools to avoid design flaws.
Priority	high

Metadata Validation Tools

Lifecycle	Review
Topic	Tooling
ID	REQ-REVIEW-TOOLING-VALIDATION
Description	Ensure that the metadata schema is accurate, complete, and compliant with predefined standards. This can be done, for example, through metadata schema validation tools which check that data registries can display and compare metadata, standardize mandatory fields for meaningful comparisons, and balance user experience with data comparability.
Creation date	2024-09-23
Linked terms	http://vocab.deri.ie/cogs#Validation https://w3id.org/vair#Validation http://data.businessgraph.io/ontology#validationRule
Solution idea	OBO-Foundry, OOPS!, ...
Priority	medium

Metadata Record

Metadata serialization formats shall be storable in a way that supports SPARQL federation

Lifecycle	Implementation
Topic	Metadata Record
ID	REQ-IMPL-RECORD-STORAGE-FEDERATION
Description	Metadata shall be queried easily among federated SPARQL endpoints, to improve findability. Queries should function with either native or virtual endpoints.
Creation date	2024-09-19
Linked terms	https://schema.org/SearchAction https://schema.org/EntryPoint https://schema.org/query https://schema.org/includedInDataCatalog http://edamontology.org/data_2080 http://edamontology.org/format_3748 http://edamontology.org/format_2195
Solution idea	Triple store databases easily provide SPARQL endpoints and therefore federation capabilities. Alternatively metadata can be stored in a way that allows for virtual SPARQL endpoints to achieve the same effect.
Priority	high

Metadata serialization formats need to be standardized

Lifecycle	Implementation
Topic	Metadata Record
ID	REQ-IMPL-RECORD-FORMAT-STANDARDS
Description	Make sure that metadata is stored with a standardized serialization format, so most tools and frameworks natively support parsing and serializing it
Creation date	2024-08-15
Linked terms	http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/NCIT_C171252 http://edamontology.org/format_1915 https://schema.org/encodingFormat
Solution idea	This means the preferred serialization formats are RDF/XML, JSON-LD, Turtle, N3 and Ntriples. Nevertheless, other standardized formats as XML, JSON, YAML and TOML are also valid and can be used.
Priority	high

Metadata record submodules storage structure

Lifecycle	Implementation
Topic	Metadata Record
ID	REQ-IMPL-RECORD-METADATA-SUBMODULE-STORAGE-STRUCTURE
Description	Submodules will need to reference each other and a flat way of storage is superior if multiple submodules might reference the same submodule
Creation date	2024-10-22
Linked terms	https://schema.org/DefinedTermSet (A submodule is a Defined Term Set that contains metadata fields relevant to the topic of the submodule) https://schema.org/inDefinedTermSet (could use this to note if a term belongs to more than one submodule) https://schema.org/citation (could use this property of a Defined Term Set to track other sets that it references)
Solution idea	Use JSON \$ref in JSON and the respective URIs in RDF based file formats
Priority	high

Guidelines for applications using or creating metadata records

Lifecycle	Integration
Topic	Metadata Record
ID	REQ-INTEGRATION-RECORD-APPLICATION-GUIDELINES
Description	Allow developers to get going with the integration of metadata in their applications quickly, with a clear set of requirements or guidelines on how to integrate and work with metadata records. All applications that want to work with the standard are obliged to follow these guidelines.
Creation date	2025-01-31
Linked terms	N/A
Solution idea	Extrapolate a subset of the requirements on this page and format them on some kind of online documentation. This can further include the use of certain services or libraries for form generation etc.
Priority	Low

Metadata UI needs to be simple and streamlined

Lifecycle	Use
Topic	Metadata Record
ID	REQ-USE-RECORD-SIMPLE-UI
Description	Don't annoy or scare users with complex forms or workflows as this will prevent them from entering data altogether. Simple and streamlined processes and UIs are key.
Creation date	2024-08-15
Linked terms	https://w3id.org/mod#browsingUI http://www.w3.org/ns/ui#style
Solution idea	Provide either a wizard/survey like form with multiple small pages or a dialog with a chatbot rather than a form and use modern web frameworks to build the UI.
Priority	High

Simplify linking between metadata records

Lifecycle	Use
Topic	Metadata Record
ID	REQ-USE-RECORD-SIMPLIFY-LINKING
Description	For easier navigation and understanding relations between multiple (data) artifacts - it is necessary to allow linking between metadata records easily. Users are not likely to manually look up relations themselves. As a result any user interface should assist the user in finding appropriate potentially related metadata records automatically.
Creation date	2024-08-15
Linked terms	http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/OBI_0000800
Solution idea	Search for strategies how to identify metadata records with a certain degree of similarities, such that a service can propose them to be added as a related metadata record. (Use the OEP scenario comparison as a foundation)
Priority	Low

Metadata record value languages

Lifecycle	Use
Topic	Metadata Record
ID	REQ-USE-RECORD-LANGUAGES
Description	Ontologies do support annotation in multiple languages, so any user interface shall be allowed to present metadata in any given language as long as the formal serialization is again in the standard language. Controlled vocabularies might also provide translations for a given item.
Creation date	2024-11-07
Linked terms	http://purl.org/linguistics/gold/Language http://purl.org/dc/terms/language http://schema.org/Language
Solution idea	User interface code can use the respective language annotations for labels when displaying both field names and selected (controlled) values
Priority	Low

Metadata usage documentation shall be understandable for users that need to fill or read metadata

Lifecycle	Use
Topic	Metadata Record
ID	REQ-USE-RECORD-DOCUMENTATION-STAKEHOLDER-USERS
Description	The workflow documentation must provide helpful information to users without data management background and shall allow everybody to get started with metadata annotation.
Creation date	2024-11-07
Linked terms	N/A
Solution idea	This is hard to measure, so for now just involve end users in the design of the documentation.
Priority	Medium

Metadata serialization format validation

Lifecycle	Review
Topic	Metadata Record
ID	REQ-REVIEW-RECORD-FORMAT-VALIDATION
Description	Validation of metadata records improves the quality of metadata. Therefore, the used record serializations must allow for standardized validation mechanisms. Validation needs to be done in two stages (client and server) to first improve UX and second guarantee record conformance
Creation date	2024-08-15
Linked terms	http://vocab.deri.ie/cogs#Validation http://def.seegrid.csiro.au/isotc211/iso19115/2003/metadata#Format http://simile.mit.edu/2003/10/ontologies/vraCore3#measurementsFormat http://open.vocab.org/terms/json
Solution idea	JSON schema and JSON-LD can be used in conjunction to validate input metadata records. If using other semantic formats the superior validation of SHACL can be applied. Web user interfaces often support client side validation this should be applied whenever possible.
Priority	High

Comparison of technical requirements with existing metadata standards

There are many metadata standards out there. The Research Data Alliance (RDA)¹⁶ curates a list of currently 126 metadata standards. This deliverable does not contain a systematic analysis of these against the defined requirements. Instead, this will be a short overview of what features are already supported by metadata standards that are especially relevant within NFDI and NFDI4Energy. The metadata standards that will be mentioned here are Dublin Core¹⁷, DataCite¹⁸, DCAT¹⁹, schema.org²⁰ and the Open Energy Metadata Standard²¹.

All the standards allow linkage between metadata records, however the amount of semantic expressivity for the kind of relation is limited. Per se, no metadata standard prevents the use of commonly accepted vocabulary. At the same time, the enforcement of controlled vocabularies, e.g. terms from an ontology could be further improved. All standards at least separate between mandatory and non-mandatory fields and most allow choosing from three available levels. DCAT and schema.org do provide some form of hiding fields to users if they are not relevant, which induces some kind of modularity. For DCAT there is the application profile (AP) mechanic to achieve this, while schema.org does often have optional child objects that are assigned to a property, which can be left blank if it is not relevant. Both Dublin Core and DataCite do provide XML schema files, while DCAT and schema.org are available in a semantic file format like RDF or JSON-LD. The Open Energy Metadata Standard is available as a JSON Schema instead. A couple of crosswalks for the major schemas mentioned here are available online. In general, a guideline for developers on how to integrate the schema or the metadata creation process is only sparsely available. Each of the schemas has a verbose online documentation about all their field definitions and how to use it. However, if you are not familiar with IT technologies, it will be hard to follow and apply the schema. DCAT does use many terms

¹⁶<https://www.rd-alliance.org/>

¹⁷<https://www.dublincore.org/specifications/dublin-core/>

¹⁸<https://datacite-metadata-schema.readthedocs.io/en/4.6/>

¹⁹<https://www.w3.org/TR/vocab-dcat-3/>

²⁰<https://schema.org/docs/schemas.html>

²¹<https://github.com/OpenEnergyPlatform/oemetadata>

from Dublin Core and this is visible in the documentation and schema, but has no specific visualization for it. None of the metadata standards provides a detailed ontology-based solution to employ controlled vocabularies. It is limited to mostly pattern-based expressions and also does not allow mechanisms to limit the values of fields further depending on the domain. The metadata schemas and the documentation are all well versioned.

A dedicated service to create metadata records in these schemas is not provided by the standardization bodies themselves. It is always integrated in solutions that use the schema, respectively. The same applies for potential exports in other formats or the provision using OAI-PMH.

The serialization format of the metadata records is not specified explicitly in the standards, though most do support JSON or XML. None of the standards function as metadata registries, so the most technical requirements can not be applied to the standard but the platforms that use them instead. However, this review is not part of this deliverable.

Contribution guidelines to metadata requirements

One important technical requirement for metadata in NFDI4Energy is the modularization of the metadata, so that users can have detailed metadata if necessary, but it does not increase the number of fields for any other user if that piece of metadata is not relevant.

To find the right metadata modules and to improve existing ones, it is necessary to collect the ideas of the community. This means, if you as a reader of this document have suggestions to improve any aspect about metadata in the energy domain, don't hesitate to contribute. It is not necessary to be affiliated with NFDI4Energy in any way.

Contributions shall be created using the respective GitHub repository, where you will also find further information on the ways you can contribute. The most common way to contribute is by creating an issue under the following URL: <https://github.com/NFDI4Energy/metadata-requirements/issues>. You can use the appropriate template for the type of change that you are proposing:

- New module
- Change module
- Discussion

New modules are for metadata topics that are not yet covered. This issue template needs to contain the necessary data to describe the module, as well as a description and motivation for your use case. You can find the most up-to-date schema for a module as well as additional information on GitHub inside the requirements-modeling.md file.

To give you a specific example, on how to request a new module: You are working with high resolution fault recordings, and you are missing some information that is specific to them, for example the configuration of the recording device and the specification of the used time resolution. You create the respective issue on GitHub to include all the details that a new module for this kind of datasets would require.

Module changes shall be used if you think a module needs to be extended or modified. This can for example include a new field or the modification of a controlled vocabulary. Clearly specify what attribute, module or group of attributes you are referring to and explain the changes you would make. Also describe the benefits for your use case and why you think the change is good in general. An explicit example for a module change could be the addition of metadata fields to properly describe time series data with a variable time resolution.

Discussion issues can be used for all other types of change that should be performed. It also is great if you think one of the current modules is not quite right, but you are missing a good change proposal

at the moment. Moreover, you could think something is missing in the current specification, but you do not have a clear picture of the potential solution yet.

In general, it is not always trivial to determine what data needs to be stored as metadata, is just a property of the annotated data itself or should go into the verbose documentation of your data set. As a rule of thumb, consider someone else looking for data on your topic or a related one: Does it help to search or filter for the attribute you are thinking about right now? If yes, then it should go into the metadata. If not, then consider if the attribute helps another user understand your particular dataset. Then it should be added to the documentation of the dataset. In the last remaining case, the attribute is just a part of the inner workings of your dataset. So just keep it in your data.

Glossary

- ABCD** Access to Biological Collection Data
- API** Application Programming Interface
- ARC** Annotated Research Context
- BFO** Basic Formal Ontology
- CDM-light** Common Data Model-light
- CEDAR** Center for Expanded Data Annotation and Retrieval
- CIDOC-CRM** International Committee on Documentation - Conceptual Reference Model
- CMDI** Component MetaData Infrastructure
- DCAT-AP** Data Catalog Vocabulary - Application Profile
- DCAT** Data Catalog Vocabulary
- DDI** Data Documentation Initiative
- DwC-A** DarwinCore Archive
- EGA** European Genome-Phenome Archive
- FAIR** Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable
- FHIR** Fast Healthcare Interoperability Resources
- GHGA** German Human Genome-Phenome Archive
- HL7** Health Level 7
- JSON-LD** Java Script Object Notation - Linked Data
- JSON** Java Script Object Notation
- LIDO** Lightweight Information Describing Objects
- MIABIS** Minimum Information About Biobank data Sharing
- NFDI** German National Research Data Infrastructure
- OAI-PMH** Open Archives Initiative Protocol for Metadata Harvesting
- OLAC** Open Language Archives Community
- PID** Persistent Identifier
- RDA** Research Data Alliance
- RDF** Resource Description Framework
- RDM** Research Data Management
- REMBI** Recommended Metadata for Biological Images
- RFC** Request for Comments
- RSMD** Research Software MetaData Guidelines

RWTH Rheinisch-Westfälische Technische Hochschule Aachen

SHACL Shapes Constraint Language

SKOS Simple Knowledge Organisation System

TEI Text Encoding Initiative

TS4NFDI Terminology Service for NFDI

XML Extensible Markup Language

maSMP machine-actionable Software Management Plans

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